

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACADEMIC COMPETENCE, PERCEIVED TEACHER STUDENT RELATIONSHIP AND PROCRASTINATION IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The objective of study was to investigate the relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. After the review of the literature following hypotheses were formulated 1). There will be a significant relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student's relationship, and procrastination in universities students. 2). Academic competence would predict perceived teacher student's relationship, and procrastination in universities students. For this study total 300 participants including 151 male and 149 female were selected through convenient sampling. The data was collected from university students of Gujranwala, Lahore and Sialkot. In order to collect the data Academic Competence scale Student-Instructor Relationship Scale and Students Procrastination scale were applied and cross-sectional research design was use to investigate relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students Regression analysis was use to find out academic competence is a predictor of perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. The findings of the study have shown that the both formulated hypotheses were approved and in 1st hypotheses findings significant relationship between variables ($P < .05$) while in 2nd hypothesis it has been indicated that academic competence is a significant predictor of teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students ($P < .05$). A substantial body of research indicates that psychological and psychosocial factors influence behavior.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between academic-competence, perceived teacher-student relationship and procrastination among university students. Besides having academic competence, the other significant constructs of university students are procrastination and perceived teacher-student relationship which happens to be the prerequisite of students for the

adequate functioning with their emotions as well as the accomplishments. Academic competence is arguably one of the most important predictors of a student's success among academic predictors (Elliot & Dweck, 2005). It has to do with proficiency in various fields of learning. On an academic level, academic competence is a clear description of how a student could manage or manipulate abilities,

information to reach an educational goal. It adds cognitive abilities, study skills and motivational and other skills supersedes to the curriculum (Zimmerman, 2008).

Within the context of a classroom, teachers have an important function of helping students acquire the necessary skills and competencies of the subject matter they are teaching. These students may need assistance from a well-designed instructional model, formative evaluation, and materials appropriate to several levels. In addition, supporting a positive learning culture and a growth mindset helps students become more resilient as well as proactive to their studies. Academic competency is an integrated phenomenon which includes will power, self-control, mental faculties and learned skills. If these issues are well understood and appreciated, the students stand to benefit a great deal in achieving their academic objectives (Dweck, 2006).

University students from various regions and countries differ greatly in academic ability. As in Pakistan, depends on things like institutional support, socioeconomic situation, and educational level. Research suggests that Pakistani college students frequently struggle with insufficient means, obsolete curriculums, and lack of support systems, all of which may affect their academic competence (Iqbal & Bhatti, 2020). Several students are driven to excel academically by a strong cultural stress on education despite these difficulties (Shahzad et al., 2021). Worldwide, university student academic competence is often better in nations with strong support programs and well funded educational systems. Advanced educational policies and practices in such nations as Finland and Singapore frequently result in high levels of academic performance among students (OECD, 2019). In contrast, pupils in poorer countries might have problems like those in Pakistan UNESCO in 2020 notes limited availability of excellent materials and educational assistance and poor access to them.

According to Robinson and Clark (2018) found that academic competence improves self efficacy and confidence among pupils, therefore enabling them to confront difficult problems and endure in the presence of difficulties. If students believe in their ability to succeed academically, they are more prone to establish ambitious goals, search for learning

chances, and maintain their efforts (Adams, 2019). Greater mental health, including low level of stress, anxiety, and feelings of academic related pressure, is connected with academic competence (Brown & Garcia, 2018). Higher levels of happiness, inspiration, and general happiness come from students who feel proficient and able in their academic endeavors (Jones et al., 2021).

By fostering a positive learning environment, teacher-student connections also aid in the development of academic competency. Students are more likely to participate actively in the learning process and take responsibility for their academic progress when they perceive that their teachers value, respect, and support them. Student behaviors and attitudes toward learning are also greatly influenced by the perceived quality of the teacher-student relationships (Hamre & Pihl, 2017).

Teachers are the primary facilitators of learning and the ones that engage pupils in adaptive behaviors in the classroom. An interpersonal relationship of understanding and support between teachers and students is the autonomy-support style. With this teaching style, the student perceives that the teacher gives him or her autonomy to choose the activity among different possible alternatives, which will facilitate the possibility of developing greater competence and promote positive functioning in the classroom. On the other hand, with the controlling style, teachers will try to control and intimidate the students. They will use authoritarian language, impose pressure, and be rigid in their connection; as a consequence, there will be poor performance in the classroom along with a loss of competence (McKenzie & Schweitzer, 2010).

Teacher-student relationships are fundamental to creating an effective learning environment. Positive interactions between teachers and students can link to high motivation, better academic performance, and a greater sense of connection in with academic community. Research has shown that positive teacher-student relationships are linked to higher educational achievement. Those who see their teachers as encouraging and compassionate are more likely to be involved in their education and have more academic drive. Moreover, these children tend to fare better academically since the positive

relationship can offer the motivation and direction required to succeed (Roorda et al., 2011).

Among students, procrastination is shaped by both academic competence and teacher student interactions. Different issues related to their academic surroundings, personal qualities, and developmental stage make university students especially liable to procrastination. Steel (2007) defines procrastination as deliberately postponing a planned course of action while expecting undesirable outcomes; it is a common problem among college students everywhere. Knowledge of these components is utterly essential for handling the repercussions of procrastination on academic performance and interactions between teacher and student. Voss (2003) contends that the independence, deadlines, and heavy workload character of college education can compound procrastination. Personal variations in motivation, time management ability, and self control as well as biological factors influence student's procrastination. Students with poor self awareness who struggle with setting long term goals and resisting instant pleasure could find themselves procrastinating (Sirois & Pychyl, 2013). The transition to college marks a key developmental stage characterized by new independence, increased demands, and scholastic challenges. Still working on their self management abilities and adapting to the demands of advanced education, many students are more inclined to procrastinate (Klassen et al., 2008).

Globally, procrastination is also widespread among university students. Research conducted in Italy with 450 university students found a significant correlation between procrastination and poor time management and meta-cognitive strategies. The study indicated that male students were more likely to procrastinate compared to female students, primarily due to differences in these skills (Limone et al., 2020). Moreover, Jara (2023) thorough analysis found that more than 50% of students globally suffer from procrastination, which has adverse effects on their cognitive wellbeing.

Among students in Pakistan, avoidance is a major problem. According a survey on 755 pupils from several colleges in Punjab, about 57 percent of the students labeled themselves as habitual procrastinators. Among the reasons for this high rate

were bad time management, a fear of failing, and lack of motivation (Khan et al., 2020).

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim and objectives of this study will be followings.

- To find out the relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in universities students.
- To predict the effect of academic competence on perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in universities students.

Rationale of the study

One needs to examine how university students' perceived teacher student relationships relate to academic ability and procrastination since these variables could influence student wellbeing and academic success. Three variables were influencing the others. University students' success is quite dependent on their academic competence that is, their level of mastery crucial for meeting academic requirements. Handling the extra work and sophistication of college classes depends on these abilities. The quality of the teacher student interaction is a major influence on the academic results and experiences of college students. Good relationship with your teachers could lead to better academic performance, engagement, and motivational level of more senior nature. Positive teacher student interactions might improve student's motivation and involvement, hence raising their academic grades (Roorda et al., 2011). Often times, university students have trouble with procrastination, therefore lower grades and increased anxiety. Knowing and dealing the reasons behind procrastination could raise the academic results of pupils. Strong self regulation abilities found in students with great academic ability enable them to effectively handle procrastination.

Prevalence rates from overseas are encapsulated herein. US university students who reported poor academic competence totaled 45.6 percent (Kuh et al., 2010). Hattie and Timperley (2007) found that 30.4 percent of Australian pupils encountered academic problems. According to Cassidy (2016),

25.9 percent of UK youths said they were deficient in academics. Conversely, 70.1 percent of US students said they have a good relationship with their instructors. Furrer and Skinner (2003) found that 60.5% of young people in Canada said their teacher student association was good. Steel (2007) found that 75.4 percent of British students procrastinated.

According to research, 55.6% of Pakistan's college pupils said they were struggling with academic competence. Among students 31.4% had educational problems including low motivation and bad time management (Rahman et al., 2017). Prevalence rate of university students at perceived teacher student relationship, on the other hand, was that 62.2 percent of Pakistan's pupils said their teachers were warm (Hussain et al., 2018). Ali (2020) found that 25.8% of pupils had a bad teacher student relationship, which resulted in disengagement and bad academic performance. 85.7 percent of Pakistan's college students procrastinated (Iqbal et al., 2019). 34.6% of pupils noted chronic procrastination, which resulted in major scholastic problems (Khan et al., 2018).

Hypotheses

1. There will be a significant relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student's relationship, and procrastination in universities students.
2. Academic competence would predict perceived teacher student's relationship, and procrastination in universities students.

Research Methodology

This section provides a comprehensive guide to the selection and targeting of data, as well as ethical considerations, rapport with participants, and trust. It also covers statistical analysis, technique, operational definitions of variables and terminology, and measure descriptions.

Research setting

The data was collected from university students of Gujranwala, Lahore and Sialkot.

Sampling technique

Convenient sampling technique was used in this study.

Research design

The investigation was conducted using a cross-sectional study approach. In order to investigate a relationship between academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. Regression analysis was use to predict and estimate the relationship between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables.

Participants

Research population was university students. Sample size was N=300 in which 151 was male and 149 was female. Sample's minimum age was 18 years and maximum 28 years with marital status of sample as married students are 44, unmarried 222, divorced 20 and 12 are separated students. Both joint and nuclear family system was selected joint and nuclear family system, where 103 students mark joint family system and 197 students represent nuclear family system with lower 30, middle 242 and upper socio economic system 28.

Inclusion Criteria

The criteria for inclusion included the subject's structures that were necessary for the current study design. Participants who met the study's specific requirements were chosen in order to reduce sampling error.

- Research was conducted only on university students.
- Both male and female were included.
- Participants in this particular study included respondents who were married, divorced, single, and separated.
- Respondents were selected from a range of economic backgrounds.
- Sample must doing BS and MS degree in university.
- University student's age range was 18 to 28.

Exclusion Criteria

To avoid errors and address sampling-related issues, as well as to control for potential factors affecting outcomes, several participants were excluded from the present study based on specific criteria.

- Mentally disable students was excluded.

- Age range under 18 and above 28 were excluded.
- School and college boys and girls were excluded.
- Student under metric and intermediate were excluded.

Measures

Demographic form

Personal information form was developed by examiner. Demographic form consisted on name/initials, age, gender, marital status, department, semester, siblings, birth order, family system, occupation, father's education and occupation, mother's education and occupation, socio economic status, physical and psychological illness, email and university name.

Academic competence scale

Academic Competence scale is developed by Ayesha Jabeen & Sana Afridi in 2017-2019. It is consisted on 38 items that represents study skills, Communication managing and self spiritual. Higher score represent greater competence in students.

Student-Instructor Relationship Scale

The Student-Instructor Relationship Scale was developed by Creasey & Jarvis in 2009. This scale has 36-item instrument that asks respondents to rate various aspects of their relationship with their instructors on a 7-point Likert scale (1 being strongly disagreed with and 7 being strongly agreed with). In the report, a factor analysis produced two distinct domains, the first of which had eleven items that loaded well on the factor (.50 or greater), indicating how close or connected the student felt to the instructor.

Eight items in the second factor loaded well (.50 or higher), reflecting students' worries about their ability to be accepted by their teachers and their value as students (e.g., "I worry a lot about my interactions with this instructor; "I'm afraid I will lose this instructor's respect"; "I am nervous around this instructor"; "I worry that I won't measure up to this instructor's standards"). Because this factor contained items that reflected anxiety concerning the student-instructor relationship, this factor was labeled the Instructor Anxiety dimension. Higher scores reflected a generalized anxiety regarding a

relationship with the instructor, whereas lower scores reflect less threatening perceptions of this affiliation.

The third factor contained 17 items that reflected feeling of discomfort, lack of trust and perceived favoritism (e.g., "The instructor seems to only appreciate certain students", "Sometimes this instructor's mood is unpredictable", "I don't feel comfortable opening up to this instructor").

Student's Procrastination Scale

To measure procrastination, Student's Procrastination Scale (SPS) will be used that developed by Qandeel Mahmood & Sara Subhan in 2013-2015. This scale is consisted on 32 items and 3 point likert scale. Items are rated on 0 to 3. Higher score reflected greater procrastination in students.

Procedure

Prior to everything research problem was identified as variable with the help of supervisor. Clinical psychologist discussed research topic according to feasibility, originality and utility. After that topic was finalized then we have started work on it. First of all permission was sought from the authors of each questionnaire to use their tool. Then clinical psychologist makes a list of universities in Sialkot, Gujranwala and Lahore and approaches it. Permission was also taken from universities from where participants were recruited for data collection. The purpose of research topic and introduction was explained with higher authority of universities then sign consent from them. After that we explained research purpose with university students and informed consent was taken from individual participants. Firstly, demographic questionnaire was administered. Then a set of questionnaires about academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination were administered to each participant to record their responses. One set of questionnaire was given to each participant. Informants were told that their given information would be kept confidential and would be used only for research purposes. After the administration of scale, research data was collected and out the data in SPSS. Result show significant relationship between the variables including the academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and

procrastination in university students. Academic competence is a significant predictor of teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. Result also shows that there is a significant gender difference existed between male and female paramedics. This study may limit the generalizability of findings to other cultural contexts. Future studies should aim to recruit diverse samples from various cultural backgrounds. Future studies should prioritize the development and evaluation of evidence-based interventions to support university students' academic success and well-being. After the completion of scoring the whole data was tabulated on the Microsoft Excel sheet. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, V 12.0) was used to analyze data.

Ethical consideration

The responsibility of a researcher to follow the ethical rules while conducting a research. Permissions were taken from the authors of the assessment tools that are to be used in this research. Permission was taken from the authorized persons of universities. It was assured to the participants that the results would be used for the research purpose only. Consent was taken from the participants by consent form. Informed consent will be taken from the participants. All the participants will be assured that their confidentiality and private information would not be revealed. The participants will be given the right to withdraw from participation and terminate at any time they wish. Dignity and respect of every participant will be maintained. The obtained data from participants will be used only for research purposes. The targeted sample was not pressurized to take part in research. The results of the research were reported completely and accurately.

Operational definitions of variables

Academic competence

"Finally also presenting a willingness to learn, adapts, and persevere in spite of difficulties and setbacks is the capacity to handle academic activities, accomplish educational objectives, build self efficacy and confidence in one's academic abilities" (Adams, 2019).

Perceived teacher student relationship

"Defined by closeness, support, and respect and including emotional, mental, and behavioral aspects, the quality of the interpersonal relationship between teachers and students" (Hamre & Pianta, 2016).

Procrastination

"Knowing that the delay could affect the quality and timeliness of the job or project and cause guilt, anxiety, and stress, voluntary delays or postponements of an intended course of action sometimes prevail" (Steel, 2007).

Results and Discussion

The section on outcomes based on the interpretations of collected data from students studying at university within the Gujranwala, Sialkot and Lahore via Scales to assess the academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. The researcher used correlation statistics to assess the responses to the review's objectives, regression analysis to know the how Independent variable academic competence predict teacher student relationship and procrastination,

Table 4.1: Demographic Characteristics of Variables (N=300)

	N	%
Gender		
Male	151	50.3
Female	149	49.7
Age	Minimum 18 years	Maximum 28 years
		Mean age 22.497
Marital status		
Married	44	14.7
Unmarried	222	74

Divorced	20	6.7
Separated	12	4.0
Family system		
Joint	103	34.3
Nuclear	197	65.7
Socio economic status		
Lower	30	10
Middle	242	80
Upper	28	9.3

In table no. 4.1 demographic characteristics of variables is described. Numbers of participants were 300, including 151 male and 149 female, with minimum age 18 years and maximum 28 years. The mean of the age is 22.497. After that table show marital status of sample as married students are 44,

unmarried 222, divorced 20 and 12 are separated students. Then table show joint and nuclear family system, where 103 students mark joint family system and 197 students represent nuclear family system with lower 30, middle 242 and upper socio economic system 28.

Table 4.2: Reliability table (N=300)

Scale Name	Items	Alpha
Academic competence scale	38	.938
Instructor connectedness	11	.799
Instructor anxiety	8	.853
Others	17	.813
Students procrastination	32	.945

In the table no 4.2, Reliability of the scales are described including the academic competence scale which has scale having 38 items with .983 alphas. Student instructor relationship scale having 36 items

has 3 sub scales, instructor connectedness is with .799, instructor anxiety is with .853 and other items are with .813 alphas. The students procrastination scale which has scale having 32 items with .945 alphas.

Table 4.3: Correlation among academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students (N=300)

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Academic Competence	68.95	18.55		.053	-.45**	-.36**	-.56**
Instructor connectedness	50.58	10.47			-.005	.19**	-.001
Instructor anxiety	30.22	9.66				.80**	.66**
Others	66.63	17.20					.49**
Procrastination	34.94	18.15					

**p<.05

The table no 4.3 shows that there is a significant relationship between the variables including the academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. Table shows that there is positive

relationship between academic competence and instructor connectedness with 68.95 mean and 18.55 standard deviation, instructor anxiety .45** other items of student instructor relationship scale p is -.36** and students procreation p -.56**.

Table shows that there is negative relation of instructor connectedness $p < .005$ with mean 50.58 and standard deviation 10.47 with instructor anxiety and students procreation $p < .001$ but has positive significant relationship with other items of student instructor relationship scale $p < .19^{**}$.

The above table shows that instructor anxiety scale has positive significant relationship with other items of student instructor relationship scale $p < .80^{**}$ and student instructor relationship scale $p < .66^{**}$. Table also shows that other items of student instructor relationship scale have positive significant relationship with student procrastination $p < .49^{**}$

Table 4.4: Summary of Linear Regression Analysis with (N= 300)

Predictor	R	R ²	Adj-R ²	F	Df	P
Academic competence	.583	.340	.331	37.925	295	.000

$P < .05$

In the table no 4.4, the findings shows that academic competence is a significant predictor of teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. The P value is .000 which is less than the .05 that shows academic competence is

significantly predict teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students. The R value is .583 and predictor R² .340 and Adjusted R .331 of the academic competence frequency value is 37.925 and DF is 295.

Model	Sum of square	Df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	34960.4	4	8740.1	37.925	.000 ^b
Residual	67984.8	295	230.4		
Total	102945.3	299			

a. Dependent Variable: scores

b. Predictors: (Constant), scores, scores

Table 4.5: Coefficients Summary of Linear Regression Analysis with academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students (N=300)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P
	B	SE	B		
Constant	89.889	5.178		17.359	.000
Instructor connectedness	.129	.089	.073	.1456	.146
Instructor anxiety					
Other	-.067	.186	-.035	-.358	.720
Procrastination	-.119	.092	-.110	-1.291	.198
	-.502	.065	-.491	-7.727	.000

$P < .05^{***}$

Table 4.5 shows that academic competence is significant predict procrastination in university students as significant value is less than .05. Coefficient summary of Linear Regression analysis shows that academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastination in university students.

Discussion

In the discussion chapter, we thoroughly examine the results and their underlying causes. The objective of the results is to determine the main elements contributing to these remarkable results. Since the next part looks into how academic ability influences procrastination as well as teacher student

relationship in university students as well as teacher student interaction.

For university students, many issues seriously affect their performance, psychological state, and general health. For students, one of their main worries is academic competence, which is shaped by motivation, learning techniques, and prior academic preparation (Zimmerman, 2000). Lower motivation, higher stress, and anxiety level may result in procrastination among students with academic competence issues (Steel, 2007). In turn, procrastination can worsen academic issues by accelerating poor grades, lowered self esteem, and raised stress levels (Tice & Baumeister, 2007).

Moreover, students can have problems in their interactions including those with teachers, peers, and love partner. Wentzel (2008) notes that poor interactions with teachers may result in lowered drive, heightened stress, and anxiety, while peer relationship problems might result in loneliness, seclusion, and reduced sense of belonging. Particularly if they are unhealthy or unfulfilling, romantic partnerships may be a source of stress, anxiety, and emotional upheaval.

University students could also suffer other issues including money worries, problems with time management, and mental health issues. Financial pressure can cause lower academic performance, reduced motivation, and anxiety levels while problems with time management can result in increased stress level, reduced efficiency, and procrastination (Kuh et al., 2006).

Hypotheses I of the current study is accepted on the basis of the information gathered from this research. That stated "University students would display major association between academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship, and procrastination". Positive relationships boost motivation and engagement and students with low academic competence may suffer from procrastination and time management, making assignment and test preparation difficult to complete and difficult course work. Depressed academic performance results from difficult equilibrium of work and schoolwork together with anxiety or mental health problems, particularly among stressed students.

Accepted as Hypotheses II was: "Academic competency will foretell student teacher relationship

and university student procrastination." Procrastination in students and a relationship could worsen if one's academic competence is difficult in a few ways. Lack of academic ability can lower one's self esteem, therefore opening the door to unhappy connections or people pleasing habits. Increased stress and anxiety from academic issues can cause students to withdraw or become more irritable, negatively affecting their relationships. Students lacking academic competence could find it hard to effectively express their requirements or worries to teachers, classmates, or love interests, therefore creating misunderstandings and stress. Comparisons with others when one is academically challenged can make one competitive and reduce empathy and cooperation in relationships.

Students with academic competence problems, on the other hand, might be afraid of failing, which will lead to avoidance behaviors and procrastinating. Reduced worth from academic difficulties makes it harder for students to start and complete assignments, thereby contributing to procrastination. Poor academic competency among students may make it hard for them to use time wisely, therefore resulting in procrastination and lowered output. Perfectionism resulting from academic difficulties may cause students to procrastinate because of concern of not meeting their lofty goals.

Summary

For university students, many issues threaten to compromise their overall university experience, personal wellbeing, and academic performance. Three major issues that students usually face include these. Academic competence is the capability of a student to achieve academic goals and complete tasks well. Many factors could contribute to university students' lack of academic competency. Trying to balance extra curriculum activities, part time jobs, and social life with school obligations could lead to poor time management and lower grades (Martinez et al., 2020). For academic success self restraint skills including goal setting, self monitoring, and self evaluation may be challenging for university students to learn yet are essential. Secondly is teachers students relationship (Zimmerman, 2000). Another consideration in rating students' academic success and general satisfaction is their relationship as

teachers. Still, some pupils may find it difficult to form good rapport with their teachers. Students can find it hard to form a personal connection with their professors given the size of university courses (Kuh et al., 2006).

The results seen are dependent on several variables, which are treated in depth in the sections that follow in this chapter. Still, it is vital, as pointed out near the end of the thesis and listed below, to acknowledge several restrictions in the study. The study has restrictions including the observation that its findings cannot be extrapolated for all individuals and that data gathered across several Punjabi cities does not cover all of Pakistan. Many elements contribute to these observed findings, and the rest of the chapter offers a thorough explanation of these origins.

Conclusion

In university students, this research showed a notch of academic competence, perceived teacher student relationship and procrastinate. This survey has 300 respondents, including students from several cities living in Lahore and Gujranwala, both male and female. Studies show that many difficulties at institute can cause problems with social interaction, self esteem, relationships with peers and instructors, and rejection anxiety, among other issues. The common psychological traits of students are still difficult to ascertain. Many research points to psychological and psychosocial variables affecting behavior. Research suggests that in the university student experience, academic competence, teacher student interactions, and procrastination are closely connected. University students' academic success and general satisfaction depend critically on their academic performance. Good student teacher interactions promote intellectual ability whereas procrastination limits it. Conversely, academic skills and teacher student interactions can affect procrastinating.

Limitations

The sample of the study was taken from several universities situated in several places; therefore all of Pakistan could not be covered. The study's sample size is limited to a particular socioeconomic group, and the subjects could not exactly reflect the range of

student encounters. This field depends on correlation designs, which restrict the possibility of showing causality among elements. Future studies should employ experimental or longitudinal techniques to help better grasp the causal relationships among academic competence, teacher student contacts, and procrastination. Different cultural settings may not find as much value in the findings of this research. Future studies should strive to recruit varied samples from numerous cultural backgrounds. Moreover, the research relies on self report instruments which might be restricted and prejudiced. Future studies need to be grounded on behavioral markers to provide a better understanding of the relationships among academic performance, teacher student contacts, and procrastination. By concentrating only on academic competence, teacher student relationships, and procrastination, the subject is oversimplified. Future research should take into account other pertinent points including motivation, self efficacy, and emotional intelligence that will enable a more nuanced grasp of the sophisticated interactions among these variables. Future research ought to give first place to the designing and assessment of evidence based treatments meant to promote the general wellbeing of university students and their academic performance.

Discussing major behavioral concerns, subjects might self report bias, leading to socially acceptable answers that do not absolutely reflect their reality. The cross sectional nature of this research could complicate understanding of the development over time of these behavioral characteristics since it only captures one point in time in the participants' life. Not completely considered in this study are external elements like socioeconomic condition, cultural background, and access to support facilities that may also affect participant wellbeing. Appreciating these restrictions could guide further studies to learn more about the problems students face from peers, colleagues, mentors, and other sources.

Recommendations

While the current study successfully addressed several significant factors related to academic competence, teacher-student relationships, and

student procrastination, certain areas remain unexplored and warrant further investigation.

- Due to time constraints, the scope of variables and the number of participating universities were limited.
- Future studies should consider incorporating a broader range of variables and include a larger and more diverse sample to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, as this research was conducted in only three countries, it is recommended that similar studies be carried out on a wider international scale to capture cultural and contextual differences.
- Future researchers should also explore longitudinal designs to examine the long-term impact of interventions. To further support academic success, future work could investigate the effectiveness of institutional strategies such as mentoring programs, student-centered teaching methods, and the promotion of extracurricular involvement in reducing procrastination and improving educational outcomes.

Implications

Important and long lasting results could come from studies on university students' academic competence, teacher student relationships, and procrastination. These could be some of the consequences of the research.

- Examples of these are online events, peer support groups, and therapy sessions where people might speak freely about their experiences and get help.
- The findings of the research could back initiatives meant to assist students in attaining self esteem, good relationships with teachers and peers, competence, positive self images, self acceptance, and empowerment.
- Considering these consequences helps the study to give a more complete understanding of student difficulties and to offer access to constructive treatments and support services that may help to improve their quality of life.
- Students who are supported academically and given a favorable learning environment will likely have lower dropout rates and higher retention.
- Where they will be expected to work independently and carefully manage their time,

improving academic competence and decreasing procrastination can better equip students for the job market.

- Workshops held at many institutions will help to lower anxiety and stress. Improved mental health and overall wellbeing can follow from reduced anxiety and stress, which in turn results from improved academic skills and less procrastination.
- Counseling with students should also help them to develop stronger coping techniques, hence improving their mental health and general wellbeing. Supporting students' academic growth and mental health calls for universities to create help resources such as tutoring and guidance.
- Universities ought let professors improve their teaching skills and encourage good teacher student partnerships by means of development opportunities.
- To help students' academic growth and lower delays, universities should institute plagiarism and academic dishonesty rules that up academic honesty together with other such policies.
- Counseling and workshops also performed with pupils who find it useful since they do not hesitate to ask for assistance from teachers, teaching assistants, or their peers when struggling with assignments, develop effective study behaviors, parse tasks into smaller increments, established achievable goals and deadlines, use time management techniques etc.

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